

THE GENDER OF COUNTABLE AND UNCOUNTABLE NOUNS

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Abstract:

In Albanian and English we have three kinds of gender: masculine, feminine and neuter. In Albanian language we have this concept for gender: *“Gjinia është një nga kategoritë gramatikore më karakteristike për emrat në gjuhën shqipe. Nga natyra e saj, ajo dallohet nga kategoritë e tjera të emrit, nga numri, rasa dhe nga kategoritë e shquarsisë dhe të pashquarsisë, sepse i kundërvihet mashkullore-femërore dhe asnjëse...”*ⁱⁱ, it's same and with English: *“a grouping of nouns and pronouns into classes' masculine, feminine and neuter”*ⁱⁱⁱ. The gender can show and function in both of numbers singular and plural. The nouns of masculine, feminine can ends with consonants or vowels. The gender (definite) of English are augmented with articles. It can show before the noun, pronoun that can substituted with pronoun /ai, ajo – he, she / or ky, kjo, ai, ajo – it (father, **man, son, boy, Tom, brother, Mr. John, /he/**). The noun and pronoun can have the gender but the adjective or verb cannot have.

Keywords: gender, countable and uncountable, singular, plural, nouns

1. The masculine nouns

The masculine nouns on Albanian usually ending with the consonant e.g.

- **student, hotel, ballkon, film, tren, lis, mal, gur etc.,**

or with vowels e.g.

- **ë: djalë, burrë, djathë, lumë, Kolë, Dedë etc.**
- **i: ulli, flori, qiri, shiri etc.**

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ⁱⁱ Fatmir Agallari, **Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe**, Tiranë, 2002, p.88.

ⁱⁱⁱ A S Hornby, Christina Ruse, **Oxford student's dictionary of current English**, New York, 2001, p. 263.

- **e: pe, dre, dhe** etc.
- **u: dru, kërceu, hu** etc.
- **a: pasha, baba, aga** etc.
- **ua: thua, përrua, krua (njeri-u, veri-u, baba-i, atdhe-u, dru - druri, sy - syri, zë - zëri)** etc.

The English has the same structure of masculine nouns with Albanian, it can be used with consonants or vowels e.g. father, uncle, brother, nephew, duke, god, hero, friend, student (common), boyfriend, male student etc. In both of languages the nouns are used in both numbers. The plural is used by means of suffixes or changes in stem sounds.

In Albanian language and English the most common methods of plural word-formation is by adding a plural suffix to the singular form. The nouns usually ending with a consonant in the indefinite form or in definite with /-i, -u/ e.g.

- **emër-i, gur-i, qytet-i^{iv}, mik-u, shok-u, krua-kroi, përrua-përroi, mure – walls, lisa – oaks, burra – men, desh – rams, natë – nights, miq – friends, zogj – birds, brigje – hills, atë – fathers** etc.

The definite nouns in English language usually make the article /**the**/ and it is contrast with Albanian because the definite nouns in Albanian are usually the suffix e.g.

- **djalë – djali – boy - **the** boy, libër – libri – book – **the** book.**

The definite nouns between Albanian and English are the full contrast because English has /**the**/ article that can show before the noun, so Albanian has definite articles or ends (suffixes) **-i, -u, -a, -të^v**.

Both of languages can make the plural nouns. It can be used with suffixes. The formation of the plural of masculine nouns is quite complex and usually can be formed with suffixation. The Albanian language has a lot of suffixes (more than 140) that are productive for too creative the new plural nouns e.g.

The plural is also formed with **-e**. With this suffixes usually can be created or found the abstract nouns. All the nouns that end with suffix **-im**, as well as borrowed words that end with **-ion, -um, take -e, in** or in the plural e.g.

- **aksione – aksions, leksione – lectures, albume – albums, stadione – stadiums, simpoziume – symposiums, vendime – decisions, mendime – thoughts, studim-e, qytet-e – cities, seminar-e, hotel-e, kat-e – floors, dokument-e – documents, tunel-e – tunnels, kanal-e – canals, shtete – states, katunde – villages, vende – places, elemente – elements, ideale – ideals, hotele – hotels, tunele – tunnels, zakone – customs, motive – motives, sheshe – fields** etc.

^{iv} Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, [The gender](#), Turqi, p.2

^v Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, [The function of noun phrases \(...\)](#), Wien, p. 116.

In Albanian language the plural is also formed with –a e.g.

- **telefon-a, gjel-a, krimb-a, dema – bulls’, trupa – bodies, pëllumba – pigeons’, topa – balls** etc.

The plural is also formed with –ë e.g.

- **shok-ë, anëtar-ë, doktor-ë, dhëmbë, lek-ë, artist-ë, arsimitar-ë – educators, formular-ë – forms, artist-ë – artists, punëtor-ë – worker, studentë – students, drur-ë – trees, fshatar-ë – villagers, beqarë – bachelors, berberë – berbers, doktorë – doctorës, policë - policemen** etc.

“Me sy të mbyllur **doktor** Gurametoja priste vendimin.”^{vi}

- **a: gjel-a, telefona, derra, dema – bulls, qingja – lambs, tipa – types, trupa – bodies, motora – motors, trëndafila – roses, rripa – slopes, trupa – bodies, bilbila – whistles, emra – names, numra – numbers** etc.
- **e: qytet-e, hotel-e, seminar-e, pus-e, vende – place’, kate – floors’, palate – apartments’, festivale – festivals’, male – mountains’, hotele – hotels’, sheshe – fields’, motive – motives’.**
- **nj: bari-nj, kushëri-nj, ari-nj, gjuhnjë – knees’, thonj – fingernails’, langonj – hounds’** etc.
- **enj: lumë –lumenj – rivers’, lëmë-lëmenj, përrua- përrenje – brooks’, budallenj – fools’, maskarenj – knaves** etc.
- **inj: shkëmb-shkëmbinj – rocks, drapërinj – sickles, gishtërinj - snakes, shkop-shokpinj, zotër-zotrinj, ari-nj, gju-nj, hero-nj** etc.
- **ër: prindër - parents, vëllezër – brothers, robber - captives, mbretër – kings, nipër – nephews** etc.

The plural of some nouns is marked only by a change in the stem vowel, usually from /a/ or /e/, or sometimes opposite of them e.g.

- **a/e: dash (ram)-desh, çjap (billy)-çjep, ka (ox) – qe, gardh (fence) – gjerdhe** etc.

There are in Albanian three sub-types of the plural type formed by the politicization of the velar consonant g and /k/ into /gj/ and /q/ e.g.

- **mik-miq (friends), bujk-bujq – farmer, peshk – peshq – fishes, cak-caqe - limit, bllok – blloqe – block, tog, togje – pile, treg – trgje – market, park – parqe – park, varg – vargje – rangs, zog- zogj, murg-murgj, breg-brigje - hills, shteg – shtigje – pass.** It’s contrast with English.

Both of languages have regular and irregular noun forms for to creative plural. English language has not the same form with Albanian because in English we have the

^{vi} Ismail Kadare, **Darkë e gabuar**, Tiranë, 2008, p.50.

suffixes **-s, -es** for to creative the plural nouns **boy - boys, dog - dogs, bus - buses, name – names** or irregular forms **man - men, woman - women, tooth – teeth** etc. It's contrast between English and Albanian.

The same forms in both of languages are for the regular and irregular nouns.

2. The feminine nouns

The Albanian language has a lot of feminine nouns that ending with vowel or consonant and the suffixes is the most usual process of formation plural forms. The most productive suffixes are **-a, -ra** etc. The following nouns are in plural (with the suffixes) **e.g.**

- **fusha – fields, lodra – games, mjegulla – fogs, flutura – butterfly, motra - sisters** etc.

The feminine nouns in Albanian language usually can make the suffixes and the most productive are: **-ë, -e, -i, -a, -o, ël, ër, -eshë, -ë, -ushë, -icë, onjë** etc., for example:

- **ë -mollë, nënë, vajzë, rrobë, detyrë, dhomë-a, dorë-a, kokë-a, gjuhë-a** etc.
- **e: lule, nuse, faqe, fitore** etc.
- **i: dituri, teori, gjini, fotografi, malësi, bukuri** etc.
- **a: kinema, kala, para, hua** etc.
 - **-o: depo, dado, pallto, kosto, radio** etc. or **zemër, vegël, femër, këmbëz, vetulla.**
 - **-ël-, -ër, -e** si **vegël-a, motër-a, lule-ja, lodhje-ja.**
- **e, -eshë, -ë, -ushë, -icë, onjë** e.g: **gjysh-e, mik-e, ministër-e, doktor-ersh, plakë-ë, zonjë, arushë.**

The English language can make the feminine nouns with root of male so it can get the suffixes **-ess** e.g.

Masculine	Feminine
actor	actress
master	mistress
heir	heiress
lion	lioness
poet	poetess ^{vii} etc.

^{vii} Shkelqim Millaku, 2011, Studime gjuhësore I, Academia.edu, p.65-107.

Both of languages have regular and irregular plural form of nouns or in English we have some forms e.g.

- /-s, es/; **bus - buses, house - houses, prize - prizes, brush - brushes, punch - punches, thing - things, dog - dogs, day - days, boy - boys.**
- /-y - i/; **lady - ladies, story - stories, army - armies, country - countries, fly - flies.**
- /-y/; **day-days, play-plays, tray-trays, key-keys, boy-boys, toy-toys.**
- /-s/; **truth - truths, wreath - wreaths, mouth-mouths, path-paths.**

Irregular plural nouns: **zero - zeroes or zeros, commando - commandoes or commandos, man - men, woman - women, mouse - mice, life-lives, wolf-wolves, knife - knives, half-halves, wife-wives** etc.

In Albanian language the plural of feminine nouns can make with suffixes -a, -ra etc. for example: **bankar, vera kashtëra, nënë, (ca) nëna, një fushë (ca) fusha, një bankë (ca) banka, ditët, rrugët, udhët, derë - duar, derë - dyer, natë netë** etc.

In English language are some forms of possibility for to build the plural nouns e.g.

- -s **cat-cats, dog-dogs, day-days.**
- -y--i: **baby-babies, story-stories, lady-ladies.**
- s, z, c, xh, zh in plural gets suffixes -es; **glass - glasses, place - places, bush - bushes, branch - branches** etc.
- -f, -ves, or -s e.g. **leaf - leaves, knife - knives, roof - roofs, shelf - shelves** etc.

The irregular nouns: **woman - women, fisherman - fishermen, child - children, ox - oxen, foot-feet, tooth - teeth, goose - geese, mouse - mice** etc.

3. The neuter nouns

The neuter nouns exist in both of languages. In Albanian language we have e.g. **kryet, të ecurit, të menduarit, se foluri brumë, drithë, dyllë, mish, miell (from adjective) të zisë, të bardhtë, të ftohtë (from verb) të folurit, të qeshurit** etc. This is same in English e.g. **book, house, desk, tree, wall, a street, a flower, a table, a fork, a pen, a spoon, love** etc.

We have in both of languages a lot of nouns that are “ambigen” for example in Albanian: **male, malet tona, qytete tona, qytete të mëdha, vende malore, vendim i drejtë, djepi, ligji, busti, naftë, program, loti, thekër** etc.

In English it is same for example: **friend, girlfriend or boyfriend, child, partner, writer, professor, teacher, student, speaker, pupil, person** etc. The animal nouns e.g. **bull - cow, drake - duck, horse - mare, dog - bitch** etc.

The plural form of the neuter noun **kreu - head, chief, krerë - heads, or krerë bagëtish - heads of cattle** it is change **ye - e** and suffix **-rë**.

Personal dual gender is a large including, for example, the following: **artist, fool, musician, speaker, student, teacher, writer, professor, person, parent, neighbour, friend, doctor, cook** etc.

4. The number of nouns

In both of languages the noun has two numbers: singular and plural. In English language we can see in the following some forms of singular and plural nouns, too.

one book	two books	one watch	two watches
one boy	two boys	one church	two churches
one problem	two problems	one house	two house
one thing	two things	one bus	two buses
one shop	two shops	one dish	two dishes
one name	two names	one glass	two glasses
one flower	two flowers	one box	two boxes ^{viii}

The structures of English and Albanian general forms are the same e.g:

- **një dyqan - one shop; two shops - dy dyqane, një emër - one name - two names** etc.

In Albanian and English we have some nouns that can have the same structure only in singular e.g. like with abstract nouns:

- **dashuri - dashuria, guxim - guximi, uri – uria, Kos - kosi, benzinë - benzina, qumësht – qumështi, the month, year, nouns: janari, shkurti, marsi, January, April, June, October etc. matematikë, histori, kimi, fizikë, Chemist, Ardita, Xhoni, Teuta, London, Parisi, veri, jug, lindje, perëndim, North, West, East, South** etc.

In Albanian and English we have some nouns that can use just in plural e.g:

- **makarona – makaronat (macaroni), krunde – krunde (bran), dhentë – sheep, viset – places, syze - syzet, gërshërët - gërshërët, miellra - miellrat, vajra – vajrat, miell, krunde, kokrrat, pantallonat, syzat, plakat, lajkat, ethet, pllakat, Alpe, Mrize, Kodër, shpatet, viset, lugjet** etc.

In English we have some nouns that are with the same structure in singular and plural:

^{viii} Shukrane Gë rmizaj, **A comprehensives handbook of English grammar**, Prishtina, 2004, p.149.

Singular	Plural
deer	deer
fish	fish
sheep	sheep
series	series
//// /	cloths
////////	goods
////////	tropics
////////	jeans
//////////	shorts
////////	glasses

The noun **sheep, deer, cod** etc., that are countable nouns do not have different between singular or plural e.g.

This **sheep** has just had a lamb

These **sheep** have just had lambs”.^{ix}

The number of nouns in the plural usually make with suffixes –es. –s for example: **Cat - cats, map - maps, boy - boys, girl - girls, case - cases, house – houses** etc. By the examples we can consider in Albanian and English it’s possible to see the similar or the contrast between two languages.

5. The countable and uncountable nouns

In Albanian and English language we have countable and uncountable nouns. The countable nouns are all the nouns e.g.

- **Prishtina (not Pristina), Shkupi (not (Scupi), Kosova (not Kosovo) Drini, Morava, libër, shkollë, mësues, mielli, uji, plakat, lajkat, etnet** etc, or in English: *“I bought some chairs, tables, and desks. In other words, I bought some furniture”*.^x

Nouns can be broadly into a small number of classes which have meaning and grammatical behaviour. There is an important distinct common and proper nouns. Common nouns can be countable and uncountable. Countable nouns refer to entities which can be counted, they are singular and plural forms (**a cow, two cows**) etc.). Both

^{ix} Sideny Greenbaun (...), **A student’s grammar of the English language**, London, England, 1990, p.95.

^x Batty Schramper Azar, **English grammar**, Washington, 2006, p.107.

in the singular and plural there is a contrast between definite and indefinite forms (**a cow, two cows, the cows**).

Countable nouns have both singular and plural forms, referring to one or more than one entity, respectively.

Uncountable nouns refer to entities which cannot be counted and uncounted for number. Though they do not combine with the indefinite article, the contrast between an indefinite and definite form (e.g. milk, the milk) ...^{xi}

Countable nouns are same in both of language: We can find large number of countable nouns for example:

Person	businessman, journalist, yachtsman,
Concrete objects	boat, present, vacuum cleaner,
Actions	event, move, race,
Other abstractions	contribution, result, rule

It needs to be stressed again that countability is not a simple reflection of things observed in the external world. For example, even a countable noun such as thing is used not only with reference to discrete concrete objects, but also to abstractions which do not so obviously or naturally come as distinct entities see the use of these things in the following example: I have just got it confirmed, but these things take time.

In Albanian language we find plurals noun for example:

- **karrikë - karrika, libër - libra, shtëpi - shtëpa** etj.

So, a countable noun in English has plurals and can be used:

- **a/an. a chair - chairs, a book - books, a house – houses** etc.

6. The uncountable nouns

Uncountable nouns have plurals (Albanian and English, too), and cannot normally be used with e.g. **air, water, English, weather**.

She speaks good English. (Not. She speaks good English).

Ajo e flet mirë anglishtne. (Jo. Ajo e flet një anglishte mirë).

In English the article a, an can use for to make the noun in singular and /a/ used before the noun that begin with consonant and an used before the words that begin with vowel.

^{xi} Douglas Biber, Sitg Johansson, **Grammar of spoke and written English**, London, England, 1999, p.245.

She speaks good **English**.

It's terrible weather. (Not. a terrible weather).

In English and Albanian we have some nouns that are countable and uncountable e.g.

I'll have a cup of **coffee**, please. Did you remember to buy **coffee**?

We use common nouns to categorize or label people and things. They are countable and uncountable. We can use countable common nouns in the singular, with a/an and each, or in the plural, with number and many.

Do you have a black **pen** or a **pencil**?

We usually use uncountable common nouns when we talk about an abstract concept, or activity, a substance or a material. Uncountable nouns are not used with a/an or in the plural. We can use uncountable nouns with no article (a) and much (b).

a. Her poem is about flying, freedom and bad luck. (not. a bad luck).

b. They have food clothing, but they don't have much water. (not waters).

“Countable nouns can be singular or plural and are normally used to refer to people, creatures and objects, or actions and events, which can be thought of as separate individual things e.g. actor, bird, car, man, party, problem etc.”^{xii} Uncountable nouns are used with singular verbs, but not to refer to individual things. They are not typically used with a/an. We use uncountable nouns to talk about substance and materials, abstracts ideas, qualities and states or activities e.g. chess, tennis, work, education, freedom, love, meat, petrol, rice etc.

The examples **ice, love, time arrival, contact, news, time feedback, theory, importance** are types of meaning which can be countable and uncountable nouns: substances (air, ice), emotional and other (news, receivership, contact); qualities (importance), events (arrival). Many nouns which are basically uncountable also have countable with difference meaning. We have some examples: time (denoting a particular occasion or a period in history), air (denoting a tune or a type of appearance or manner).

^{xii} George Yule, **Oxford practice grammar**, Oxford, 2008, p. 74.

“The things we can count are called count nouns. The things we cannot are called non count nouns. A non-count noun does not have a plural form and we cannot put a number in front of it. We never use **a/an** with non-count nouns. Count nouns example: **a book - books, one book - two books, some books, a lot of books, many books, a few books or non-count nouns singular: sugar, same sugar, a lot of sugar, much sugar, a little sugar.**^{xiii}

The use of a noun as countable or uncountable is lexically restricted difference in meaning varies to a large extent with the individual noun. The short form of countable is C and for uncountable is U.

Both can be C/U nouns, but in the contest we can know different of meaning. For example:

- a. Six **teas** please. (C)
- b. It was in fact impossible to be strenuously diligent after one of Mrs Sutton’s **teas**. (C)
- c. Plant beverage include **tea, coffee, wine, ...**and sweet beverage (U)
- d. We learned to eat brown **rice** and yogurt and to tolerate kasha and add-tasting teas.

The countable instances of tea are used in the sentence “a cup of tea’ /a/ “a type of tea’ and “a small meal usually served in the afternoon with a cup of tea” b. The uses illustrated in /a and d/ are often found with other basically uncountable nouns. Countable and uncountable nouns we have and abstract nouns, for example **education, freedom,** etc.

7. Plural uncountable nouns

Although it may seem to be a contradiction, there are plural uncountable. These are morphologically plural nouns which do not vary for number and do not combine with numerals:

She wears those jigsaw-type **clothes, trousers** usually.

Unite nouns are in a way the opposite of collective nouns: rather than provide a collective reference for separate entities, they make it possible to split up an undifferentiated mass and refer to separate instances of a phenomenon. Both types of noun provide alternative ways of viewing

^{xiii} Kathryn Church, **American English workbook**, Tirana, 2002, p.25.

and referring, collective nouns with respect to countable and until nouns with respect to uncountable^{xiv}.

With bit of and piece of are the most productive, each combining with well over 100 different collocates.

Unit Noun	Selected Collocates ^{xv}
act of	adultery, kindness, folly
bit of	beef, cake, cheese, sugar, paper
chip of	glass, ice, paint
chunk of	chocolate, meat, gold, data
game of	cards, chess, golf, tennis
grain of	corn, dust, salt, sand
item of	clothing, information, equipment
loaf of	bread
lump of	clay, soil, butter, fat
piece of	cake, chicken, wood
pair of	clippers, glasses, plants
slice of	pie, ham, bread etc.

Here are some groups of nouns:

1. Countable nouns with singular (and plural) in –is, analysis, analyses, crossroads, series.
2. Other nouns with singular and plural the same: **trout, deer, fish, salmon.**
3. Nouns that have a plural without –s after a number hundred (two hundred) million (two million)...
4. Nouns with singular in –f (e), plural in –ves, **calf - calves, wife - wives, knife - knives, self - selves.**
5. Nouns with irregular plurals: **man - men, woman - women, child - children, foot - feet.**
6. Uncountable singular nouns ending in –s (normally no plural) **billiards, economics, politics, gymnastics.**
7. Plural nouns with no singular e.g. **arms, clothes, people, trousers, congratulations** etc.
8. To form the plural nouns, add –s, **table - tables, room - rooms, desk - desks,** etc.
9. If the noun ends s, sh, ch, x, or z add es, **glass - glasses, dish - dishes, church - churches, box - boxes** etc.

^{xiv} Douglas Biber, Sitg Johansson, **Grammar of spoke and written English**, London, England, 1999, p.250

^{xv} Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, [The compound nouns](#) (...), European Journal of Education Studies, Vo.2. Iss.3.

10. If the noun ends in a /y/ preceded by a vowel (a, e, i, o, u) only add /s/, **day-s, guy-s, key-s** etc.
11. If the noun ends in on/o/ preceded by a consonant, add -es. **Potato - potatoes, hero - heroes, tomato - tomatoes, radios, zoo - zoos.**
12. If the noun is a compound, make the noun plural, not the modifier: **mother-in-low --- mothers-in-low, piece of cake - pieces of cake.**
13. If the number, litter, or sing is considered as a word, add 's. **1900's, (1900), 10-10'së ABC-ABC's.**
14. Some nouns are same in the singular and plural, **fish - fish, deer - deer, sheep - sheep.**
15. Some nouns are always plural: **mathematics, pants, cloths** etc.

Plural and uncountable nouns with and without /the/ (**flowers**) **the flowers, music- the music.**

1. We do not use /the/ before a noun when we mean something in general: I love flowers (not, the flowers). I prefer classical music to pop music. (Not, the classical music....)^{xvi}.
2. We say /the/ ... when the mean something in particular. I like your garden. The flowers are beautiful. All the students in the class like their teacher.
3. We do not usually say with the names of countries, cities, and village. Franca not the France, Europe not the Europe, or New York, Prishtina, Paris etc.

We can say with /the/ names which include works like: **republic, kingdom, states. The United Kingdom, the United States of America, the Republic of... Regions: the north of England, the south of Spain,** etc.

Regular count nouns		Irregular count nouns	
Singular	Plural	Singular	Plural
Lemon	Lemons	Man	Men
Song	Songs	Woman	Women
Egg	Eggs	Child	Children
List	Lists	Person	People
Cake	Cakes	Foot	Feet
Orange	Oranges	Tooth	Teeth
Idea	Ideas	Mouse	Mice
Glass	Glasses		
Dish	Dishes		
Sandwich	Sandwiches		
Box	Boxes		

^{xvi} Raymond Murphy, **English grammar in use**, Cambridge, 1992, p. 148.

“Some words (English) borrowed from Latin and Greek keep their foreign plural, or their maybe alternation with regular plural forms.

Latin nouns ending –us	Latin nouns ending in –um
alumnus - alumni	aquarium - aquaria
calculus - calculi	curriculum - curricula
terminus - termini	millennium - millennia
	index - indices ^{xvii}

Greek nouns ending in-is:

Axis – axes, crisis - crises, diagnosis - diagnoses.

The build of nouns in singular and plural, masculine, feminine and neuter, countable or uncountable are augmented for both of languages for reports that have the same or different.

Conclusion

The aim of this study is to point out of similarities, differences, contrasts or generation of gender between Albanian and English language by comparing different (function) parts of speech. The first contrast of gender between two languages are the cases, the second are definite and indefinite, the third are articles, the fourth are prefix and suffix, the fifth are endings etc. The full contrast between two language was seen at the possessive case, in Albanian language can be realize with the article (for *masculine, feminine* and *neuter*) **i** (m), **e** (f), **të** (n) and **së** (f) or with definite endings **-i, it, -in, -ve** (m), or **-u, -ut, -un** (m), but in **English** this case used with the article **/the/** for definite nouns (m, f, n), so between two languages it is the contrast because it has two forms of possessive and usually used after the noun e.g. Mary's book, Time's house, students', worker's, children's, women's^{xviii}, This is Arta's jacket, This is my mother's jacket. This is the dog's food. If a plural noun does not end in /s/, add 's. women's, men's, children's etc. This phenomenon of grammar is the morphology contrast between two languages and in the future we will see the function (syntax) of the gender in the sentence.

^{xvii} Douglas Biber, Sitg Johansson, **Grammar of spoken and written English**, London, England, 1999, p.286

^{xviii} Shkelqim Millaku, 2015, *Anglisticum Journal (IJLLIS)*, Volume: 4, Issue:4, p 298.

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